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Legal Consolidation of the Principles of Court Activity in the Context of Reforming the State's Judicial System

У статті визначено правове закріплення принципів діяльності судів в умовах реформування судової системи держави.

Зазначено, що правове регулювання принципів діяльності судів забезпечується значною кількістю нормативно-правових актів, які відрізняються один від одного за назвою, порядком прийняття, юридичною силою тощо.

Підкреслено, що міжнародно-правові акти в частині, що стосується діяльності судів, в більшості з них під поняттям «принципи» розуміють обов'язкові для виконання правила поведінки. У тій чи іншій мірі у різних інтерпретаціях знаходять своє відображення різні категорії принципів, які, на нашу думку, необхідно закріпити на законодавчому рівні в нашій державі, адже належна правова регламентація принципів діяльності, зокрема і адміністративної, сприятиме оптимізації функціонування системи судів у цілому.

Наголошено, що найважливішу роль у системі законодавчих актів, які регулюють діяльність судів, відіграє Закон України «Про судоустрій і статус суддів». У Законі визначено і закріплено поняття, основні її завдання, принципи діяльності, основні обов'язки та права, правовий і соціальний захист судів. Закон України «Про судоустрій і статус суддів» визначає організацію судової влади та здійснення правосуддя в Україні, що функціонує на засадах верховенства права відповідно до європейських стандартів і забезпечує право кожного на справедливий суд.

Ключові слова: *правове закріплення, принципи, адміністративна діяльність, суди, реформування, судова система держави, Україна.*

The article defines the legal consolidation of the principles of the activity of courts in the conditions of reforming the judicial system of the state.

It is noted that the legal regulation of the principles of administrative activity of courts is provided by a significant number of normative legal acts, which differ from each other in terms of name, order of adoption, legal force, etc.

It is emphasized that in the part of international legal acts related to the activity of courts, in most of them, the concept of "principles" means mandatory rules of conduct. To one degree or another, various interpretations reflect different categories of principles that, in our opinion, must be established at the legislative level in our country, because proper legal regulation of the principles of activity, in particular the administrative one, will contribute to the optimization of the functioning of the court system as a whole.

It was emphasized that the most important role in the system of legislative acts regulating the administrative activity of courts is played by the Law of Ukraine "On the Judicial System and the Status of Judges". The Law defines and enshrines concepts, its main tasks, principles of activity, basic duties and rights, legal and social protection of courts. The Law of Ukraine "On the Judiciary and the Status of Judges" defines the organization of the judiciary and the administration of justice in Ukraine, which operates on the principles of the rule of law in accordance with European standards and ensures everyone's right to a fair trial.

Keywords: *legal consolidation, principles, administrative activity, courts, reformation, judicial system of the state, Ukraine.*

Formulation of the problem. Legal regulation of the principles of administrative activity of courts is provided by a significant number of normative legal acts, which differ from each other in terms of name, order of adoption, legal force, etc.

In our opinion, the study of regulatory support for the activity of courts and the legal consolidation of the principles of administrative activity of courts is of scientific and practical importance, as there are currently no comprehensive studies of this problem.

Improvement of the legal establishment of principles, which will fully comply with international norms and standards, will help to increase the efficiency and coherence of the work of the courts, and as a result, the trust and change of the population's attitude towards them.

Therefore, we believe that the existing legal framework for court activity (as far as its principles are concerned) does not meet modern needs, therefore there is an urgent need to improve it through certain changes.

In order to reflect our own visions regarding the improvement of the legal consolidation of the principles of the administrative activity of the courts, we consider it necessary to consider the existing regulatory legal acts, in which the principles of the courts' activity are fixed to one degree or another.

Literature review.

General issues of court activity were the subject of scientific research by V.B. Averyanova, M.I. Anufrieva, G.V. Atamanchuk, O.M. Bandurky, Yu.P. Bytyaka, V.M. Harashchuka, O.P. Hetmanets, S.M. Husarova, V.O. Zarosylo, T.O. Kolomoets, V.K. Kolpakova, A.T. Komzyuka, V.V. Martynovsky, O.I. Mykolenko, O.M. Muzychuk, O.V. Negodchenko, O.I. Ostapenko, V.P. Petkova, V.M. Plyshkina, O.S. Pronevycha, O.Yu. Sinyavska, A.O. Sobakarya, H.P. Yarmaki, O.N. Yarmysh and other scientists. However, despite a sufficiently large number of scientific works on various areas of court activity, the issue of legal consolidation of the principles of the administrative activity of courts in the context of reforming the judicial system of the state is covered fragmentarily, within the framework of a broader legal issue, accordingly, the problems of the theoretical, organizational and legal nature of their activity remain unresolved, which emphasizes the expediency of scientific research on the researched issues.

Thus, the need to improve and systematically renew the activity of courts, forms and methods of their activity, the legal consolidation of the principles of administrative activity of courts in the conditions of reforming the judicial system of the state, and the lack of complex scientific studies of this issue determine the relevance and indicate the need for a comprehensive study of the legal consolidation of the principles of administrative activity of courts in the conditions of reforming the judicial system of the state.

The purpose of this article is to determine the legal consolidation of the principles of the administrative activity of courts in the conditions of reforming the judicial system of the state.

The results

The system of legal acts that regulate the principles of court activity can be divided into 3 main groups:

1. Constitution of Ukraine. Has the highest legal force. Laws and other normative legal acts are adopted on the basis of the Constitution of Ukraine and must comply with it [1].

The Constitution of Ukraine does not establish the principles of the administrative activity of the courts directly, but stipulates the general principles of the organization of the activities of state bodies. Since the courts are part of the executive authorities, the principles established by the Constitution are fundamental for the administrative activity of the courts. Example:

- the principle of the rule of law (Article 8);
- the principle of equality before the law (Article 24);
- the principle of impartial treatment of people (Article 34);
- the principle of affirming and ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens (Article 3);
- the principle of respect for dignity (Article 28);
- the principle of social justice (Article 1).

Therefore, these basic principles should also be defined in other normative legal acts that regulate the activity of courts.

2. International legal acts. In international legal acts, in the part that concerns the activity of courts, in most of them, the concept of "principles" means mandatory rules of conduct. To one degree or another, various interpretations reflect various categories of principles that, in our opinion, must be established at the legislative level in our country,

because proper legal regulation of the principles of activity, in particular the administrative one, will contribute to the optimization of the functioning of the court system as a whole.

3. Laws of Ukraine. The most important role in the system of legislative acts regulating the administrative activity of courts is played by the Law of Ukraine «On the Judicial System and the Status of Judges». The Law defines and enshrines concepts, its main tasks, principles of activity, basic duties and rights, legal and social protection of courts. The Law of Ukraine "On the Judiciary and the Status of Judges" defines the organization of the judiciary and the administration of justice in Ukraine, which functions on the principles of the rule of law in accordance with European standards and ensures everyone's right to a fair trial [2].

In our opinion, the system of principles is defined very successfully in the Law of Ukraine «On the principles of preventing and countering corruption» [3].

In accordance with Article 3 of this Law, the activity of preventing and combating corruption is based on the principles of:

- rule of law;
- legality;
- comprehensive implementation of legal, political, socio-economic, informational and other measures;
- priority of preventive measures;
- the inevitability of responsibility for committing corruption offenses;
- openness and transparency of activities of state authorities and local self-government bodies;
- public participation in measures to prevent and counter corruption, state protection of persons who provide assistance in the implementation of such measures.

In our opinion, within the scope of the Law, such a list of principles is exhaustive, because it

reflects the basic principles of state institutions authorized to prevent and counter such a socially dangerous phenomenon as corruption [4, p. 251, 5, p. 174, 6, p. 135].

Summing up, it should be noted that during the analysis of the legal consolidation of the principles of the administrative activity of the courts, we came to the conclusion that the system of normative legal acts that regulate the principles of the activity of the courts can be divided into 3 main groups:

1. The Constitution of Ukraine, which does not directly establish the principles of the administrative activity of courts, the principles established by the Constitution are fundamental for the administrative activity of courts and should be reflected in other legal acts regulating the activity of courts.

2. International legal acts that directly concern the activity of courts. In them, the category of "principles" mainly means mandatory rules of conduct, and certain principles are reflected in different interpretations.

3. Laws of Ukraine. In some of them, the legislator has very successfully defined the list of principles of court activity, in others such a category is absent or absent at all.

The principles of court activity should be enshrined in the general provisions of normative legal acts, since principles are the basis, foundation, and beginning. The principles should be general, fundamental, because they form organizational principles that determine the essence, characteristic features and general directions of court activity.

Prospective further scientific research should determine the principles of court activity in the member states of the European Union.

References:

1. Konstytutsiia Ukrainy: vid 28 cherv. 1996 r. URL: <http://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/254k/96-vr>.
2. Pro sudoustrii i status suddiv: Zakon Ukrainy 2 chervnia 2016 roku № 1402-VIII. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1402-19#Text>.
3. Pro zasady zapobihannia i protydii koruptsii: zakon Ukrainy vid 7 kvit. 2011 r. № 3206-VI. URL: <http://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/3206-17>.
4. Chumak V.V. Rol i mistse vyshchykh spetsializovanykh sudiv u systemi sudoustroiu Ukrainy. *Visnyk Kharkivskoho natsionalnoho universytetu vnutrishnikh sprav*. 2020. № 2 (89). S. 250-258

5. Chumak V.V., Tsebynoha V. Yu. Zakhyst v administratyvnomu sudochynstvi Nimechchyny prav liudyny: dosvid dlia Ukrainy. *Visnyk Luhanskoho derzhavnoho universytetu vnutrishnikh sprav imeni E.O. Didorenka*. № 4 (84). 2018. S. 173-178.
6. Administratyvna diialnist: navch. posib. / M. V. Kovaliv, Z. R. Kisil, D. P. Kalaianov ta in. Kyiv: Prav. yednist, 2009. 432 s.
7. Aver'ianov V. Zasadnyche znachennia pryntsypu verkhovenstva prava u sferi vykonavchoi vlady. *Visnyk derzhavnoi sluzhby Ukrainy*. 2016. № 3. S. 33–37.
8. Administratyvne pravo Ukrainy. Akademichnyi kurs: pidruch. dlia studentiv yuryd. spets. VNZ: u 2 t. T. 1. Zahalna chastyna / Aver'ianov V. B. (holova redkol.), Bytiak Yu. P., Zui V. V. ta in. Kyiv: Yuryd. dumka, 2014. 583 s.